

COMPARATIVE CHANGE OF WORDS IN TRANSLATION AS AN EXAMPLE OF ENGLISH AND UZBEKI

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Abstract: This article talks about the comparative change of words in the process of translation from English to Uzbek and from Uzbek to English and discusses it with the help of some examples.

Key words: Translation, linguistics, comparative analysis, compound words, lexical words, word form.

Today, in our country, special attention is paid to learning foreign languages, especially English. Several decrees and decisions on the development of foreign languages are adopted by the head of our state and our government every year. This means how important it is to learn foreign languages. Translation is the art of re-creation, a high artistic creation, even if it is a creation, it is a creation that requires research, labor, and patience from the translator, and requires hard work on various materials. The meaning of the concept of translation is very broad, because "What is translation?" Representatives of different fields give different answers to this question. One person says that translation is the translation of a book written in one language into another language, while another person considers it to be the explanation of an idea expressed in one language to people who speak another language. According to a third person, movies are also translated, so translation means translating the speech of an actor playing a role in one language into a second, third, etc.

Approaching translation from the point of view of linguistic translation studies, it can be defined as follows: Translation, which is a complex form of human activity, is a creative act of re-creating a speech expression (text) created in one language, preserving its unity of form and content, based on the means of another language. is a process. So, the speech expression created using the means of the original language is replaced by such an expression created on the basis of the laws of the translated language. In these 8 ways, the substantive and stylistic adequacy of the texts of the original and translation languages is created. Translation is a powerful tool that serves the interests of friendship, brotherhood and cooperation between peoples, and the expansion of economic, political, scientific, cultural and literary relations between them.

All of the above comments about the translation have a soul. Because each of them describes the translation from one side and serves to complete the general understanding of it. So, translation is a multi-faceted, fast-paced, complex activity. Translation is one of the most ancient types of human activity, thanks to which we can clearly imagine the history of human development in all its details. Translation accelerates the process of interaction and influence of literature of different nations. Thanks to translated works, readers enjoy the masterpieces of world literature, their aesthetic feelings increase, their tastes grow, and they develop concepts about beautiful things. Translation, as a necessary tool for the development of languages, accelerates the pace of their development, increases and improves vocabulary.

Translation enriches a person's spiritual life and expands the possibilities of the mother tongue. The achievements of comparative linguistics are effectively used in the translation. The purpose of comparative analysis in translation is to study general rules in the translation process.

Comparative analysis in translation theory is based on the facts (evidence) accepted as a result of comparative analysis of words and sentences. A comparative study of the different characteristics of words in English and words in other languages shows that there are different characteristics of words in English and other languages. The word form, the semantic structure of related words and the use of ulam in speech are different in different languages. Each language has its own lexical structure. But not in all meanings, that is, you can find a word in Uzbek that expresses the meaning of the word in English.

For example, compare the meanings of the word "hand" with the word "қол" that expresses its meaning. In addition, in the English and Uzbek languages, the related words Mangan form various artificial words.

For example: "hand" (handful, handiness), "köl" (kolle, no kolle, kolle). The verb "to take" and the words "to take" that express its meaning are incompatible in several senses.

For example: To take an exam - pass an exam; To take tea - drink tea; To take off-jechinm white; to give an examination; to have a rest; to photograph - to photograph. The semantic structure of a word in the Uzbek language may have a specific formal meaning that is not present in the English word expressing the meaning of this word.

For example: This event was a good lesson to me. The level of lexical valence of an English word is not the same as that of an Uzbek word.

For example: the Uzbek word "kotarma" can be combined with nouns such as "kol" and "chair". But the English verb "to raise" expressing its meaning can only be combined with the noun "hand" ("to raise hands", but not "to raise chair", but "to lift chair"). Several synonyms of the same type in English can be translated by one word in Uzbek.

For example: the verbs "accept, admit, adopt, take, receive" represent the word "accept". The word "artist" in Uzbek is represented by three different words in English. They are "painter, artist, drawer". The word "Blow" is translated into six words in Uzbek (hit, hit, hit, hit, knock, kick). More than 20 words in the English language express the concept of "hit". They say "blow; smack slap whack poke dig; rap; knock stroke" and h. Some languages are rich in words with significant special meanings, while others express general concepts and reject secondary meaning.

French is generally considered to be a very abstract language, while German is a language that is concrete and full of specific concepts. In German, there are three special verbs that express a common concept in French, and in French, in many cases, artificial words are used, and in German and English, more compound words are used: cendrier-ashtray, aschenbecher; theriere-tea pot... A comparative study of the structure of the English and Uzbek languages shows that a number of simple, artificial and compound words can almost correspond to each other. But when we translate English words into Uzbek, we see some differences, simple words are used more than artificial or compound words in English. The Uzbek language is rich in artificial and compound words, which, unlike the English language, are often used in speech.

Here are some sentences in English and Uzbek as examples. For example: pocket (pock), hamlet (ham), "Pock", "ham" morphemes are single (bo Min mas) morphemes, because they

do not have meaning. In short, translation is a powerful weapon that serves the interests of friendship, fraternity and cooperation between peoples, and the expansion of economic-political, scientific, cultural and literary conclusions between them.

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